

Curriculum Innovation for Immigration Contexts

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Abstract:- Immigration phenomenon in the United States has presented at least four waves throughout its history, making it one of the nations with the highest rates of immigration and generating an adaptive challenge for the educational system, which becomes more complex with transformations of society towards globalization. A curricular innovation route based on Design Thinking was created, through a qualitative action research study involving 47 teachers, 50 families, 100 students, 12 Middle School directors. The main contributions of this research consist of the integration of the constructs of global education, intercultural education, and international education, to propose a conceptual model called Trans cultural Global Education and the creation of a curricular innovation route to implement in immigration context schools.

Keywords:- Immigration, Curriculum Innovation, Global Educatio, In.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many countries have historically faced problems with rapid and consistent immigration patterns. One of the challenges created by immigration is educating the children of immigrants. The students face challenges include interrupted schooling, language, and cultural barriers, minority religious beliefs, native education levels, socioeconomic resources, and the level of acceptance or rejection of immigrants by the host country.

The ethnic and cultural diversity resulting from changing immigration patterns is reflected in the diversity of the student population in North American colleges. Research on the needs of immigrant students in schools in the United States and Canada has increased in recent decades, which demonstrates the increased interest of the scientific community in issues related to diversity and interculturality, especially since disciplines such as sociology, anthropology, psychology, ethnic studies, and education.

Education can and should play an important role in a world that is more global and at the same time more local than it was almost twenty years ago. Issues emerging from the legacies of the 20th century – unprecedented global migration, unrelenting world wars and conflicts, uncontrolled materialistic consumption, unconscionable environmental degradation, and the COVID-19 pandemic – are important questions about the cost of losses such changes necessitate, individually and collectively.

In this interdisciplinary context, the educational organization has been challenged by trends that have led to curricular reforms that are not always pertinent to the rationale, nature, and heterogeneity of the education sector. Although a curricular evolution is registered as the nature of the sector changes, it is also evident a certain resistance to

shed patterns associated with citizenship and national identity that end up affecting the migrant population. Is it possible to motivate curricular innovations for these contexts? What would be the possible ways to contribute to a change in the curricular paradigm that allows us to assume the challenges that globalization has brought with it? How to incorporate global and intercultural competencies in the curriculum that respond to the very particular and heterogeneous needs that institutions face? educational? These are some of the questions that social and educational researchers of the phenomenon of immigration have accepted and that this research seeks to resolve.

The purpose of the research is to design a curricular innovation route that allows meeting the needs identified in the educational community of Guilford County, North Carolina, considering a conceptual structure capable of recognizing the transformations that it must generate in the educational field. the phenomena of globalization and mobility in recent decades.

II. METHODS

The study was a qualitative research, implementing an action research design, under a hermeneutical - interpretive paradigm), and two types of analysis units: (i) the educational community of the Middle School level of Guilford County in North Carolina; and (ii) Public documents generated by experts in education and immigration contexts.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The main research topics registered in the literature are, among others, demographic characterizations, bilingual education, multicultural literacy (academic trajectories of immigrant students, family separation and reunification of immigrants, among others. The topics that are grouped in this cluster with the highest number of occurrences are: gender (female, male, ethnology, psychology, socio-economic factors, age, country of origin, employability, statistics).

There is a growing concern in the United States about a pedagogy capable of meeting the specific needs of immigrant students. Immigrants disproportionately experience harsh teaching and punishment situations and learning environments where they are culturally marginalized and silenced, which are not compatible with their identity, growth and development. However, these concerns are not new, nor is the migratory phenomenon, and yet the literature does not provide clear guidance to address the challenges faced by immigrant students. The literature does not clearly define the differences between the needs of black students, culturally and linguistically diverse students, minorities, immigrants, etc. (Cahill et al., 2016; Glenn, 2019; Osorio, 2018).

This means that although educators express their concern with demographic change due to increased immigration and agree that teacher preparation must respond to these changes, their speeches show a lack of knowledge of the nature and scope of the concepts of multiculturalism, interculturality and diversity. Literature that focuses specifically on the education of immigrant students tends to be biased toward second language learning. However, it ignores all the other factors that affect the learning of children and young people who are outside their environments, who must face rejections due to their customs, their beliefs, their cosmogonies, who are forced to adapt to the context that " belongs" to others (Diette&UwaifoOyelere, 2017; Lash, 2017; Soutullo et al., 2016; Sudhinaraset et al., 2017).

American schools have been the social institution most directly affected by high levels of immigration, making the task of integrating new groups of people into American society increasingly challenging. Because a large proportion of immigrant children live in urban areas, the trend is for most of them to be educated by urban public schools in low-income neighborhoods. The challenge of offering education and many other services to immigrant children in order to fully and quickly integrate them into American society presents several obstacles (Bacolod & Rangel, 2017; Lai, 2021; Parra-Cardona et al., 2019; Stull & Ng, 2016).

IV. RESULTS

A. Lexicometric Analysis

The focus groups were organized as follows: First, the research approach was introduced to the participants, presenting them with the main characteristics of the immigration contexts identified in the research and the migratory characteristics of North Carolina and Guilford County. In addition, they were presented with an introduction to the divergences and convergences between global education, international education and intercultural education found in the literature. Subsequently, the discussion was carried out through questions that addressed the following topics:

- Common practices of curriculum management in immigration contexts;
- Their perceptions about the needs of curricular management specific to immigration contexts;
- Factors to take into account to generate curricula based on global education and intercultural education.

Iramuteq software was used, which allows multidimensional analysis of texts of different nature, such as official texts, web pages, news, laws, open-ended questionnaire questions, etc. Next, the results of the interpretation facilitated by this software are presented thanks to the interpretation of the texts extracted from the focus groups through lexicometric analysis.

The lexicometric analysis of the opinions of the invited experts allows us to identify two large categories, one that is associated with educational innovation in which the relationships between innovation and teaching, resources, and students have a central place. The second category groups the concepts related to education and intercultural understanding, which in turn is displayed in five classes. Among these classes, a series of interrelationships are observed.

Fig 1: Lexicometric Experts Opinion Analysis.

Source: Iramuteq own experiment

Classes 2 and 3, which occupy 19.2% and 15.1%, relate the attitudes associated with intercultural understanding that are experienced in the classroom, such as respect, empathy, equality, trust, belonging. Class 5, with a participation of 13.8 in the recurrence analysis, which is closer to the configuration of schemes where the family has a determining role, is in turn related to the previous ones. This result is closely related to what we will analyze in the next section regarding intercultural understanding capacities in students, teachers, managers, and family members.

Fig 2: Dendrograme Experts Opinion. Source: Iramuteq own experiment

On the other hand, classes 1 and 4 participate with 14% and 17% respectively. These classes collect concepts associated with the curriculum and didactics in contexts of diversity. The socio-cultural educational development and its materialization through didactic decisions are linked in this relationship that the software throws. The dendrogram of the following figure, allows to identify the central concepts of each class, it is striking that the concepts of digital technology, curriculum, family role, trust, classroom, plural and attitude are in the center.

Against this, we recognize some of the comments made by the experts in the focus groups that academic research on immigration has focused more on trafficking, exploitation, family reunification or the general integration of migrant children, where the education remains a secondary issue. The migratory phenomenon is often included within public policies on diversity or ethnic minorities of a certain territory, often unaware that the population of migrant children and young people has specific needs that must be taken into account when thinking about public policies, such as language, cultural integration, uprooting from the country of origin, separation of families and their reunion, interruption in studies. Experts agree that the education of migrant children constitutes a great challenge that the school must face, since the educational institution is not prepared to integrate children and young people in a human rights approach where their identity and culture are respected. originally. In this aspect, the curriculum represents a point of tension that limits the intercultural dialogue between the different actors of the educational process.

The graph of factors again shows us the clusters of concepts grouped by colors and their relationships. As we can see, the topic of innovation is isolated in the lexicographical analysis, that is, in the opinions of the experts, innovation is not necessarily talked about to address the issues of education in immigration contexts. For its part, intercultural education is related to the teaching material cluster and a little with the intercultural understanding cluster. A relationship that is evident is that associated with educational schemes and attitudes of respect, trust within the classroom. Faced with this, it stands out in the opinions of the experts, on the need to support pedagogical practices in a

principle of educational equality, granting the same learning opportunities for all boys and girls and generating cultural exchanges between the different groups. In classes, migrant students can spread cultural aspects of their countries, activating curiosity and respect for diverse knowledge. Although these spaces for dialogue between other cultures exist, it is observed that it is not a priority to integrate cultural difference as a resource that can enrich learning and the implementation of the curriculum.

B. Common Practices of Resume Management in Immigration Contexts

The means and resources used do not usually promote an education that can favor the educational inclusion of immigrants.

The curricula and study plans are rigid, they do not clearly show the way in which a real intercultural education will be carried out, which prevents the necessary changes and transformations from being carried out.

The need to recognize cultural diversity and ask about the way in which it should be treated from an educational perspective is not discussed, but an education to live in plural, diverse, multicultural societies is not usually given in practice.

Bilingual education programs tend to raise the need for curricular "additions" that would involve knowledge of the language and culture of other cultural groups, which is not usually part of the institutional culture, but rather is due to isolated events.

Monocultural and homogenizing proposals prevail, which deny the consideration of differences of gender, social class, or culture.

Critical approaches understand that the development of intercultural curricula consists of offering all students instruments to understand the world from diverse sociocultural perspectives, but normally the established curricular structure leaves these purposes to the classroom and depending on the will of the student. teacher to do it.

Content referring to the cultural characteristics of different minorities in the schools is incorporated, focusing

on symbolic aspects: crafts, music, gastronomy, famous people, important dates of their cultural calendar, celebrations. These practices are generally limited to "an intercultural day" or "the week of diversity" in which the ordinary curriculum is not questioned or altered in any way.

On some occasions, it is proposed to add didactic units, topics, works, among others, to the ordinary curriculum, which does not imply a modification of the prescriptive curriculum route proposal, but it does raise the need to complete the curriculum to deal with cultural diversity.

Educational institutions are not prepared to integrate children and young people in a human rights approach where their identity and culture of origin are respected.

Although these spaces for dialogue between other cultures exist, it is observed that it is not a priority to integrate cultural difference as a resource that can enrich learning and the implementation of the curriculum.

The curriculum that is implemented in schools with migrant students does not undergo major modifications or interpretations. The curricular contextualization is reduced to the insertion of data or information isolated from other cultures, without major restructuring of it.

The absence of a planning process to be able to articulate the contents declared in the curricular framework with the cultural knowledge of migrant students is evident.

C. Needs of curricular management typical of immigration contexts.

The training of teachers for attention from the diversity that the migratory phenomenon produces, not only with training, but also with the accompaniment of experts from different areas and disciplines.

The teacher must be able to adapt their contents, processes and didactics based on the implications that immigration brings with it. It is about giving meaning to this meeting of cultures and promoting from this reality training processes that involve personal enrichment of a cognitive, ethical, emotional, and aesthetic nature.

The teacher must be able to design and produce materials based on pedagogical knowledge and the various theories and approaches that explain the teaching-learning processes in immigration contexts.

It is necessary to formulate curricula and study plans that are flexible enough to make the adjustments that are required when having immigrant students in the classroom.

Educational systems in immigration contexts must recognize and value the individual in their cultural specificity and origin, considering their language, worldview and history.

It is convenient to overcome a restrictive conception of the curriculum (focused on the specification of a plan of objectives, areas, content...) to define it as the set of experiences (implicit and explicit) that constitute the experiences of the students.

There is an urgent need for bets on the perspective of transforming the curriculum where all the curricular contents are considered from different cultural perspectives. It is crucial to choose topics that allow a diversified approach to content. An approach that helps to understand these contents in a complex way, that makes them grow and that, at the same time, cultivates fundamental attitudes and skills for interculturality: empathy, decentralized thinking, cooperative interaction, critical thinking.

In addition to cognitive understanding and the development of certain attitudes, it is necessary for students to commit their action and transfer these attitudes to responsible behavior in situations of injustice, discrimination, marginalization.

D. Key factors to generate adequate curricula in immigration contexts.

Generate safe and respectful spaces so that these types of students can express themselves freely without the risk of being stigmatized or excluded.

Open spaces of interest and motivation that lead to the exploration of cultural elements.

Promote dialogue and respect for an adequate coexistence. For this reason, it is important to emphasize the cultural elements that unify.

Generate multilingual communication strategies.

Promote interventions and empirical processes to validate the intercultural education approach.

Reconsider the conception of citizenship, rethink the school space as a scenario where cultural differences converge and respect for Human Rights is made possible.

Consider the multiple ways in which students approach learning and knowledge, without discriminating based on their origins or cultural, social, ethnic, religious, gender, learning styles and levels of knowledge.

Interculturality in the curriculum, that is, generate a dialogue between the different knowledge or positions that arise from the same topic, without hierarchizing or relieving one over the other. The foregoing can occur through thematic content, in pedagogical learning actions, through the interrelation of one or more subjects, among others, which allows enhancing critical, creative, and reflective thinking about the reality in which it is being studied. insert.

Generate actions for an intercultural education aimed at educating to live in heterogeneous contexts, create social cohesion from plurality, build community from identity diversity.

Organize socialization experiences based on values of equality, reciprocity, cooperation, integration.

Use cultural diversity as an instrument of social learning.

Provide students with skills of analysis, assessment and criticism of culture.

Represent the cultural realities of the context and favor, in practice, that students can give meaning to their daily life experiences.

V. CONCLUSION

The review of the literature in various sources allowed us to clearly recognize the phenomenon of immigration in the United States and its relationship with education. Various positions were explored, some quite critical of the colonizing place of the curriculum and its capacity for emancipation in the face of problems associated with social justice that necessarily challenge those involved in a phenomenon of this nature. This review allowed to support the research problem by identifying the needs in curricular matters that are evident in immigration contexts, among which it is highlighted to advance in the investigations that until now have focused on integrating immigrant students in a context that tends to ignore their culture, their values, and the place of their knowledge. Likewise, to recognize the phenomenon of immigration in a context of globalization that poses very different dynamics for the 21st century from those under which educational policy decisions on immigration have been considered.

On the other hand, the review allowed knowing the state of the art of the investigations, identifying three fundamental themes around which the studies are concentrated: research on socio-demographic aspects of the education-immigration relationship; research on cultural aspects of the education-immigration relationship and research on policies associated with immigration, education and citizenship, showing an absence of research that relates the issues of educational innovation and immigration. With this, it was possible to support the need for this research because it could contribute from a new perspective to the attention of the phenomenon in American schools, taking advantage of one of the most important benefits of innovation, the ability to meet an unprecedented adaptive challenge. and in the framework of the uncertainty that can generate a global and cross-cultural look at human relations with ever broader interactions.

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